

Supplementary Information

Comparative Sorption Behavior of Indian Bentonites Toward Metal Ions from Real and Simulated Municipal Solid Waste Leachates

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(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. S1. Laboratory-Scale Landfill Simulator Reactor. A laboratory-scale landfill simulator reactor was designed and fabricated to generate municipal solid waste (MSW) leachate under controlled conditions. The reactor was configured to simulate a realistic waste composition, consisting of 73% wet waste (primarily kitchen waste) and 27% dry waste (mainly wood, paper, plastics, etc.). To mimic natural rainfall infiltration, perforated pipes were integrated into the design to allow the controlled addition of water. This figure illustrates key stages in the operation of the laboratory-scale landfill simulation system. Panel (a) shows the fabricated reactor designed to replicate real-world municipal solid waste (MSW) conditions. Panel (b) depicts the collection of leachate samples generated during the simulation process. Panel (c) highlights the mixing of wet and dry waste fractions during the feeding stage to ensure uniform distribution and consistent decomposition behavior within the reactor.

(A) BT-1

(B) BT-2

Fig. S2. Amount of heavy metals present in MSW leachate adsorbed by both bentonites at various dosages. The amount of heavy metal ions sorbed per unit mass of bentonite decreased as the quantity of bentonite increased. This is primarily owed to the decrease in the active sorption sites on the bentonites' surfaces as the adsorbent concentrations increase with time.

Here, we present two images for the same experiment due to large differences in the q_e values in the Y-axis.

(A) BT-1

(B) BT-2

Fig. S3. Amount of heavy metals present in simulated MSW leachate adsorbed by both bentonites at various dosages. The amount of heavy metal ions sorbed per unit mass of bentonite decreased as the quantity of bentonite increased. This is primarily owed to the decrease in the active sorption sites on the bentonites' surfaces as the adsorbent concentrations increase with time.

Here, we present three images for the same experiment due to large differences in the q_e values in the Y-axis.

Fig. S4. Elemental analyses of both bentonites depicting their initial characterization. A) shows the XRD plots; B) represents the FTIR plots. The XRD experiment (28 Bruker AXS D8 model, Billerica, MA) was carried out to analyze the presence of predominant minerals like montmorillonite, illite, kaolinite, and quartz in the bentonites. Materials were scanned at 5° to 35° with a step size of 0.03°. FTIR analyses were performed at room temperature following the KBr pellet method over the spectral range of 450–4000 cm⁻¹ to determine the chemical functional groups present on both bentonites (PerkinElmer, Spectrum Two, Waltham, Maine).